

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

TO01000112-V1 3D geological model of the storage complex and set of structural geological maps

**Authors: Vladimír Opletal, Lenka Klímová,
Milan Pagáč (MND),
Róbert Prochác, Miroslav Pereszlenyi, Juraj Franců,
Petr Jirman, Lukáš Jurenka, Jiří Rez (CGS),
Jan Tveranger, Walter Wheeler (NORCE)**

June 2022

CONTENT

1 INTRODUCTION.....	3
2 COMPILATION AND EDITING OF INPUT DATA INTO THE REQUIRED FORMATS.....	5
2.1 Exploration and production wells data set	5
2.2 Well logs and mud logs.....	6
2.3 Seismic data set.....	6
3 INTERPRETATION OF SEISMIC DATA.....	9
3.1 Seismic to well tie.....	9
3.2 Seismic interpretation in time domain.....	14
3.3 Time surfaces construction and time-to-depth conversion of key surfaces.....	15
3.4 Seismic horizon mapping (stratigraphic boundaries), time and depth maps	21
4 CONSTRUCTION OF THE 3D STATIC MODEL.....	24
4.1 Model and grid boundary definition and fault modelling.....	24
4.2 Pillar gridding.....	25
4.3 Make horizons process.....	27
4.4 Layering	35
5 DISTRIBUTION OF PETROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES IN THE STORAGE COMPLEX.....	38
5.1 Well logs evaluation	38
5.2 Well logs upscaling	39
5.3 3D Petrophysical properties distribution	41
6 CONCLUSION	48
REFERENCES.....	50

1 INTRODUCTION

Construction of a 3D geometric model based on seismic interpretation and well results was the main task of CO₂-SPICER Work Package 2. The surfaces of most prominent lithostratigraphic units (forming the reservoir and sealing rocks of the Zar-3 CO₂ storage complex) served as the main input for the static reservoir model constructed in Petrel software. The model represents the base for subsequent dynamic modelling of CO₂, oil, gas and water behaviour within the storage complex in WP3 and WP8. The model construction flowchart (covering the geometric part of the process) is shown in Fig. 1-1.

Fig. 1-1: Flowchart showing the steps in geological model construction (geometric part).

The necessary input data was obtained from the operator of the Zar-3 oil and gas field, which is MND a.s., and from the CGS – Geofond database. They were mostly processed under WP1 „Data gathering and consolidation”. At the beginning of the task, a basic coordinate system was defined (S-42/83 = Pulkovo 1942(83) / Gauss-Krüger zone 3, similar to code EPSG 3835), to which all data within the project are transferred.

The interpretations were done partly by MND a.s., using the Petrel software by Schlumberger, and partly by CGS, using the OpendTect (dGB Earth Sciences), Petrel and MOVE (Petroleum Experts) programs, with contributions to both interpretation versions by the NORCE team.

The area where the model was built is situated in the vicinity of the Zar-3 future CO₂ storage site, where – up to now – an oil and gas field is being operated and produced by MND a.s. Two areas of different scale were chosen for the interpretations and model construction (Figs. 1-2 and 1-3).

Fig. 1-2: The working area for the simplified regional 3D geological model (red polygon).

Fig. 1-3: The working area for core reservoir 3D model, serving as input for dynamic reservoir simulations (the extent of the model – the injection zone and adjacent aquifer are highlighted in colour).

The larger-scale area (Fig. 1-2), used for more regional interpretations of geological units, is defined by a polygon chosen to cover the Zar-3 structure itself, adjacent part of the storage complex, and its close vicinity. The regional model includes the reservoir as well as its underburden and overburden.

The area of the static core reservoir model (Fig. 1-3) was chosen to cover mainly the reservoir rock saturated by hydrocarbons and a large part of the connected aquifer to allow for the best estimation of the active aquifer zone that is important for the dynamic modelling phase. The model incorporates the direct overburden of the reservoir.

The basic workflow (Fig. 1-1) is similar for both models, in some model construction sub-steps a slightly different approach was used. Chapter 2 is devoted to preparation of input data for model construction. Chapters 3.1 – 3.3 provide a detailed description of individual model construction steps used for the core reservoir model and partly also for the simplified regional model. Chapter 4.3 specifies some distinct or additional procedures used for construction of the regional model.

Fig. 1-4: Illustration of the static reservoir model of the Zar-3 structure in 3D view.

2 COMPILATION AND EDITING OF INPUT DATA INTO THE REQUIRED FORMATS

2.1 Exploration and production wells data set

The database used for construction of interpreted surfaces and bases of selected horizons and fault planes consists mainly of archival hydrocarbon well data provided by MND a.s. and the 3D seismic cube with chosen coordinates processed and prepared by MND a.s. The hydrocarbon production data provided by MND a.s. were also used for model construction as well as final reports from hydrocarbon wells covering the former geological, paleontological and hydrocarbon origin studies. Those were also used for

stratigraphy definition in all involved wells. All those archival data were gathered and saved in CO2-SPICER geodatabase for further use within WP1.

The first step was the preparation of geodetic and geological data of 22 wells and sidetracks in the area of the Zar-3 field in the EXCEL spreadsheet editor, so that they could be imported into any interpretation software: UH3, UH5, UH6, UH9, UH10, UH11, UH12, UH16, ZA1, ZA3, ZA4, ZA4A, ZA5H, ZA6, ZA6A, ZA7, ZA8AH, ZA8H, ZA9AH, ZA9H, ZA12 and ZA14H.

As part of the data preparation phase for the subsequent interpretation and the regional geological model construction, the data from CGS database and also data provided by the company MND a.s. were imported into 3D visualization and interpretation software. Some data first required editing and conversion into appropriate formats, usually using a spreadsheet or text editors. The data thus prepared were then visualized using the software available at CGS for working in a 3D environment, which includes OpendTect, MOVE and Voxler. Each of the programs used has specific features, applicable at different stages of the subsequent process of preparing the 3D geological model and creating individual outputs. In addition, more recently CGS has obtained Petrel, a powerful data analysis and interpretation tool, into which the prepared data has also been imported.

2.2 Well logs and mud logs

All well logs from the 22 wells listed above have been provided by the operator in digital form (standard LAS files) and are available in the project geodatabase. All well logs were imported into the interpretation software for further work on the 3D static geological model. The well data involve well headers (well head coordinates) and well tracks. Check-shot data were available for ZA1, ZA2 and ZA7 wells. Well log data, in particular the spontaneous potential (SP), resistivity log (RAG), gamma ray (GKA), sonic log (AK), density log (HK) and neutron log were used and analysed together with well cores and well reports for setting of well stratigraphic profiles and definition of reservoir properties.

Well log data were also supplemented by the mud log data from wells where they were available.

2.3 Seismic data set

The 3D seismic cube provided by MND a.s. represents the main input for interpretation of selected stratigraphic and lithostratigraphic units in the 3D model. 3D seismic in the area was mainly acquired for hydrocarbon exploration in the existing hydrocarbon exploration licence area. Two 3D acquisition blocks cover the Zar-3 storage site. The 3D block Uhřice 1994 covering directly the Zar-3 area was acquired in 1993-1994, while the 3D block Uhřice East was acquired in 2003. The older Uhřice 94 block was acquired using dynamite technology, the Uhřice East block was acquired using the Vibroseis technology. The basic acquisitions parameters are summed up in table 2-1.

Tab. 2-1: 3D seismic acquisition parameters for the blocks used in Zar-3 model interpretations.

3D seismic block	Uhřice 1994	Uhřice East - north part
Technology	Dynamite	Vibroseis
Recording system	Sercel SN388	I/O System Two
Trace length/Sample interval	5000 ms/2 ms	5000 ms/2 ms
Total number of sources	3882	4685
Source point interval	50 m	50 m
Source line interval	300 m	250 m
Shot hole depth	13 – 54 m	10 – 100 Hz/16 s
Total number of receivers	7506	13539
Receiver interval	50 m	50 m
Receiver line interval	150 m	150 m
Receiver lines	6	12
Active channel per line	60	50
Live channels	360	600
Nominal fold	15	30
Minimum – maximum offset	17 – 2055 m	1 – 1901 m
Total number of traces	1361287	2590298

The raw seismic data were processed by MND a.s. processing centre in Brno in 2018. The blocks were merged and the final grid of processed data has a bin size of 25x25 m. For the final block chosen for the Zar-3 project an area within Inlines 2347 – 2467 and Xlines (crosslines) 2544 – 2744 was chosen with preserved sample interval 2 ms and total time of bottom of seismic block at the level of 4,998 ms. Processing included 5D regularization for compensation of geometry anomalies caused by irregular positioning of shot points and receivers. Use of regularized data for pre-stack time migration minimizes the unwanted migration effects. The module FRENDD was used for 5D regularization incorporated in Geovation software by CGG used for seismic data processing. For final PreSTM (pre-stack time migration) the Kirchhoff method was used in raytrace version with final velocity and anisotropy model incorporated from latest processing versions. The amplitude equalization with operator 2000 ms was applied before migration. Then the RMO – high density “residual moveout” - was applied for static correction as it was still present on migrated gathers before stacking. The data were reduced by partial stacks in offset classes with step 150 m and the noise attenuation in tau-p domain was done before automatic RMO picking. The seismic cube with well trajectories is shown in Fig. 2-1.

Fig. 2-1: 3D seismic cube with well paths of Zar-3 oil and gas field and its surroundings.

3 INTERPRETATION OF SEISMIC DATA

3.1 Seismic to well tie

The first step of seismic dataset interpretation in time domain is well to seismic tie that allows converting the well data set into the time domain. Basic depth – time model based on check-shot data is the main method used for this purpose. In Zar-3 project, the ZA3 (Fig. 3-2) and ZA7 wells (Fig. 3-1) check-shot data were used for basic well to seismic tie directly in the Zar-3 field area while ZA1 well check-shot data (Fig. 3-2) were mainly used for basic seismic to well tie in the area outside of the field.

Check-shot data for the ZA7 well showing the interval and average velocities vs. depths are shown in Fig. 3-1.

Fig. 3-1: ZA7 well check-shot – measured interval velocities (left) and calculated average velocities (right) vs. depth in the well.

Time to depth curves (vertical travel time curve) measured in wells ZA1 and ZA3 provide another basis for conversion of well data from the depth to time domain and vice versa. Vertical travel time curves recalculated into two-way-time are shown in Fig. 3-2.

Fig. 3-2: ZA3 and ZA1 wells check-shot – vertical travel two-way-time curves.

Building the synthetic seismograms was the second step for the proper well to seismic tie process. Seismograms were then correlated with the real seismic traces to set the discrete reflector in 3D seismic related to the stratigraphic boundary known from the well. Sonic and density well logs were imported into the fundamental synthetic seismograms. Then the well logs were edited for despiking (removing spikes) in both logs in order to avoid any artificial events. After that, the logs were calibrated using the check-shot data (if available). The acoustic impedance was then calculated either directly from the sonic and density logs, or the sonic log (if not available for given well) was calculated from the density log. From the acoustic impedance, the reflection coefficients were derived as the main input for calculation of synthetic seismic trace.

Then, the proper wavelet has been chosen for calculation either using the wavelet extraction or using directly the wavelet parameters in several iterations. In the Zar-3 site, two Ricker wavelets were used with peak frequencies of 22 and 28 Hz, with no phase rotation as the 3D seismic cube is expected to be zero phase processed. The ZA3 and ZA4A wells synthetic traces are demonstrated in Fig. 3-3 and 3-4, where all input parameters can be observed. The synthetic trace “Synthetic 1” was calculated using 22 Hz Ricker wavelet and the Synthetic 13 was calculated using 28 Hz Ricker wavelet. The Fig. 3-3 and 3-4 show the types of seismic boundaries for further correlation and seismic interpretation in the intervals of lithostratigraphic changes.

Fig. 3-3: ZA4A – Well logs, acoustic impedance, reflection coefficients and synthetic traces.

Fig. 3-4: ZA7 - Well logs, acoustic impedance, reflection coefficients and synthetic traces.

3.2 Seismic interpretation in time domain

After well data were tied to seismic data in time domain, detailed geological interpretation of the most recently processed 3D seismic data was performed both in Xline and Inline directions covering the Zar-3 oil and gas field and its vicinity as a future CO₂ storage site. An example of stratigraphy and faults interpretation in a seismic sections is shown in Fig. 3-6 (Inline 2415) and Fig. 3-7 (Xline 2830). The seismic horizons chosen for detailed interpretation were the top of reservoir rocks (top of Vranovice carbonates), reservoir base (top of PreMesozoic), the sealing overburden of the Zar-3 storage complex built by the Mikulov Fm. (top and base) and autochthonous Paleogene (top and base), base of Carpathian Thrust Units, and the rocks forming the basement of the Zar-3 reservoir facies – the Lower Carboniferous (top), Devonian carbonate facies (top) and Devonian basal clastics (top).

Fig. 3-6: Seismic section along Inline 2415 showing the interpreted surfaces and describing the lithostratigraphical units within ZAR-3 project area.

The interpretation of seismic data was done in 3D and each 5th line was interpreted for every surface in inline direction and each 5th line was interpreted for all surfaces in Xline direction (Figs. 3-6 and 3-7). The interpretational grid density was increased to 2x2 in both directions in the direct vicinity of the Zar-3 storage area.

The faults within the area were also interpreted with the similar grid that was used for the interpretation of key seismic horizons. Some faults were used as a boundary for the static geological model grid and one major fault was interpreted in the central part of the Vranovice Fm. reservoir area.

Fig. 3-7: Seismic section along Xline 2830 showing the interpreted surfaces and describing the lithostratigraphical units within Zar-3 project area.

3.3 Time surfaces construction and time-to-depth conversion of key surfaces

From the final interpretational grid (Fig. 3-8) for each mapped horizon, the time surfaces were constructed as a main input for velocity model for the time-to-depth conversion.

Fig. 3-8: Example of final interpretational grid in 3D view – top of Vranovice Fm. grid with fault pattern.

During surface construction, the grid increment 10x10 m was used with automatic position from the input data. Input data were refined in pre-processing by smooth (cubic spline) algorithm, which kept the original points unchanged. No post-processing was used as the time surfaces were serving as an input for time-to-depth migration in the next step. All main surfaces were constructed in the same way. The time surface of the top of Pre-Mesozoic as an example is demonstrated in Fig. 3-9. The interpreted faults were lately depth migrated separately and used as an input for static model construction of the reservoir of the Zar-3 site.

Fig. 3-9: The time surface of Pre-Mesozoic in 3D view, serving as a base for the reservoir model.

Fig. 3-10: Average velocity map showing the seismic velocities used for the time-to-depth conversion of the Vranovice Fm. top surface.

The time-to-depth migration was done using the well velocity data in combination with surfaces constructed from time interpreted horizons. During TWT (two-way-time) to

Z (depth) conversion, the bi-directional model was used, the depth tolerance was set to 1 m and time tolerance to 4 ms. Average velocity maps (Fig. 3-10) were constructed and the time to depth migration was done for all key lithostratigraphic boundaries including the Base of Carpathian thrust units, Top of Pre-Tertiary, Top of Mikulov Fm., Top of Vranovice Fm., Top of Lower Carboniferous and Top of Pre-Mesozoic (Fig. 3-11). Increment of final depth surface was set at 20 m in each direction with Convergent interpolation method. Time-to-depth conversion of top of Nikolčice Fm. was done as part of the zone making process during the pillar gridding of the static model.

Fig. 3-11: Resulting depth surfaces used as input for the static reservoir model after depth migration.

Seismic interpretation for the regional model was performed in OpendTect software. After importing 3D seismic and borehole data, including well logs and stratigraphic data, and identifying lithostratigraphic boundaries with seismic reflectors, selected horizons were mapped within the 3D cube. The following horizons were mapped in 3D seismic: base of the Flysch Belt units (Fig. 3-12), base of the Paleogene (Fig. 3-13), top of the Jurassic Vranovice formation (Fig. 3-14), base of the Jurassic (Fig. 3-15), base of the Carboniferous (Fig. 3-16). By mutual combinations of the mapped boundaries, supplemented by manual adjustments based on the well results, it was then possible to construct the top surfaces and bases of all the major lithostratigraphic units (Appendix – II-11 – II-39). Boundaries in the oldest formations of the area (top of the Devonian and top of the crystalline basement) are not clear in the seismic data and due to limited number of wells penetrating these units they could not be mapped.

Fig. 3-12: Base of the Flysch Belt units interpreted in 3D seismic data.

Fig. 3-13: Base of the Paleogene interpreted in 3D seismic data.

Fig. 3-14: Top of the Vranovice carbonates interpreted in 3D seismic data.

Fig. 3-15: Base of the Jurassic interpreted in 3D seismic data.

Fig. 3-16: Base of the Carboniferous interpreted in 3D seismic data.

The geology of the area is very complex, mainly as a result of lithofacies changes in the Jurassic sedimentary record and significant erosional event in the Paleogene, which has resulted in the complete removal of Jurassic sediments to the south, south-east of the Zar-3 structure and deep incision into the Carboniferous deposits. Mapping of stratigraphic or lithostratigraphic boundaries on seismic reflectors is possible only locally, they mostly manifested in seismic data by changes of the seismic image or as toplap and onlap termination of reflectors. The Zar-3 structure itself is poorly visible in seismic data, represented by indistinct reflectors forming a bland elevation, the presence of the field is essentially indicated only by existing wells and their results, not by seismic data. In the area of the field, only the base of the reservoir (Vranovice carbonates) is more distinct, represented by a stronger reflector with a larger areal extent.

Regarding the faulting of the area, tectonic termination of the Carboniferous sediments on a prominent NW - SE trending fault, which is quite well imaged by the seismic and is also demonstrated by the drilling results has been identified (Fig. 3-16, Appendix – II-36 – II-39). In the NE part of the area, based on seismic data, there appears to be a minor fault in a roughly W - E direction that is faulting Jurassic and older rocks (Appendix – II-19 – II-35). The seismic image does not show significant signs of tectonics, overall the area appears to be more or less atectonic with a predominance of erosional processes that may have hidden or completely removed eventual older fault planes. Some indications of reflectors discontinuities in some parts of the seismic cube are short in extent, of varying irregular direction with no apparent trend, and often not very clear, indicating facies / lithology changes rather than faulting. In summary, the 3D seismic in this version of the processing does not seem to highlight, but rather suppresses, the display of possible fault tectonics.

Once the surfaces were mapped in 3D seismic, a standard conversion of the time maps to depth domain was performed using average velocity maps constructed based on values of stratigraphic / lithostratigraphic boundaries in wells, which were refined several times during the course of the work by detailed correlation of well data.

3.4 Seismic horizon mapping (stratigraphic boundaries), time and depth maps

Well log correlations tied with seismic data served as a basis for construction of geological cross-sections that supported the set-up of the regional geological model. An example – a NNW-SSE cross-section connecting wells UH11 and ZA7 is shown in Fig. 3-17.

Fig. 3-17: Zar-3 site – NNW-SSE geological profile with well logs (depth below sea level).

The horizons correlations in the seismic profiles are guided, where possible, by continuous seismic reflections, which correspond to lithological and/or stratigraphic boundaries of contrasting rock types.

These were then used for creation of time maps representing selected horizons (correlates, see chapter 3.1) that are documented by isolines of two-way-time (ms) and are subsequently converted to the depth domain using the seismic velocity model. An example for the base of the Carpathian thrust belt is shown in Figs. 3-18 and 3-19. These maps were used as input in the construction of the regional model.

Fig. 3-18: Base of the Carpathian thrust belt in time domain.

Fig. 3-19: Base of the Carpathian thrust belt in depth domain.

Since the 3D seismic surveys were performed in relatively demanding seismogeological conditions with rapid lithofacial changes, significant layer slopes, unconformities and variable seismic wave propagation rates, some parts are quite difficult to interpret. To limit these uncertainties, the depth maps were repeatedly adjusted by well data, mud logs and correlations of logging measurements.

4 CONSTRUCTION OF THE 3D STATIC MODEL

4.1 Model and grid boundary definition and fault modelling

The first step of the static geological model building was the model definition and setting of its boundary. Interpreted faults were used as grid boundary for the Zar-3 static geological model.

Fig. 4-1: Extended faults with model skeleton as a boundary set for the model.

Thus, the faults resulting from the faults interpretation were migrated to the depth domain firstly. All faults forming the model boundary had to be extended (Fig. 4-1) to cover full model depth interval, which - in this case - was -700 – 2600 m (STVD – sea level true vertical depth).

Fig. 4-2: The extended and connected faults used for the definition of the model grid boundary.

The regional 3D geological model covers most of the extent of the available 3D seismic. Surface boundaries of 3D seismic data and NW - SE line in its northern part , extended vertically subsurface to a depth of 3000 m (TVDSS), have been used as model boundaries. The vertical extent of the model is bounded by horizontal planes, one at 0 m and the other at 3000 m (TVDSS).

4.2 Pillar gridding

After the model boundary was set, the pillar gridding process has been performed in order to make a grid based on the defined faults. The pillars were inserted between the faults to provide one pillar in every corner of each grid cell. During the grid boundary setting it is necessary to set the basic grid orientation for construction of oriented grid skeleton for building of the grid cells. The I and J grid directions are set usually as perpendicular to each other (if possible). In the Zar-3 model case, the I grid direction is striking generally NNW - SSE and the J direction is striking SW - NE. The increments in I and J directions were initially set to 50 m. The skeleton grid was prepared in three levels as a top, mid and base skeleton (Fig. 4-1). Whole pillar gridding process underwent at least 12 iterations where the I and J directions increments (defining final grid density) was gradually decreased from 50 m (Fig. 4-3) to 25 m and finally to 10 m, making thus the final grid iteration horizontal cell size 10 x 10 m (Fig. 4-4). The fault layout was also tested as when using standardly defined faults the regular shaped grid cells along faults was not obtained. Finally the zig-zag type faults were generated for final model grid (Fig. 4-5).

Fig. 4-3: The initial model grid with 50 m horizontal density in I and J directions.

Fig. 4-4: Top of Vranovice Fm. horizon with final grid iteration density 10 m in I and J directions.

Fig. 4-5: The standard fault layout of the model (left) vs zig-zag type fault solution of the final grid.

4.3 Make horizons process

After the grid was prepared within the model boundary, key horizons were incorporated to the model. In the first iteration the top of the reservoir – Vranovice Fm. and the base of reservoir – top of Pre-Mesozoic surface were used to form the basic reservoir model. In the second iteration the Nikolčice Fm. was added as a zone into the basic reservoir model as the seismic interpretation was not directly possible for this part of the reservoir due to its small thickness.

The geometry of Nikolčice Fm. zone was defined and converted into a separate zone using mainly results from the wells in the Zar-3 structure where the siliciclastic facies was indicated at the base of reservoir in mud logs (Fig. 4-6). As an input for the Vranovice Fm. and top of Pre-Mesozoic, the depth surfaces from seismic interpretation were used and depth calibration was done using the well tops. Gaps were filled by the convergent gridder and the horizons were calculated in one segment. All faults were used with the active distance 100 m for conversion of depth surfaces into the model. The final model was then manually edited as the automatic surfaces/faults to model conversion was not precise due to complex geological setting of the area (Fig. 4-7).

Fig. 4-6: The Nikolčice Fm. horizon top surface with the wells in 3D view.

Fig. 4-7: The final top of the main reservoir formed by Vranovice Fm. after manual editing – 3D grid detail with Zar-3 site.

In the next step the simplified model of overburden was incorporated into the model as new zones were created, formed by the Paleogene and Upper Jurassic (Mikulov Marl) sealing formations. The depth surfaces from seismic interpretation were again used as input. Boundary faults were used for all zones, and the central fault dividing the reservoir rock was limited only to the zones of Jurassic age (Fig. 4-8). The whole model was

divided into two segments, one covering directly the Zar-3 four way dip closure structure forming the potential CO₂ storage and the second covering the more distant parts of the reservoir aquifer (Figs. 4-9 and 4-10).

Fig. 4-8: 3D grid with base of the reservoir and intersection through the enhanced grid with incorporated overburden of Zar-3 field.

Fig. 4-9: 3D view of the top of the main reservoir zone formed by Vranovice Fm. – whole grid in 3D view.

Fig. 4-10: 3D grid with top of the reservoir and intersection through the enhanced grid in segment 2.

A different approach was used in the development of the static 3D regional geological model. Given the quality and resolution of seismic data, the results of the seismic interpretation and mapping can be considered as a kind of semi-finished product that requires a lot of subsequent intervention by the geologist, adjustments and refinements to make the overall concept of the geological evolution of the area make sense and to make the maps as accurate as possible. Although this is a more complex and time-consuming process than simply using the results of seismic interpretation alone, the geology constructed in this way (which in this case is mainly the result of the work of a geologist, not just software and interpolation algorithms), is usually more precise and accurate. Therefore, after conversion of the time maps to depth domain, a number of manual adjustments were made and detailed depth structure maps and of top surfaces and bases of all selected stratigraphic / lithostratigraphic boundaries were produced (Appendix – II-11 – II-39).

Constructed maps include depth structure map of the:

- base of the Flysch Belt units
- top and base of the Paleogene
- top and base of the Jurassic
- top and base of the Mikulov formation
- top and base of the Vranovice formation
- top and base of the Nikolcice formation
- top and base of the Carboniferous

The structural maps were also produced in a version with a detailed indication of the extent of the overlying and underlying lithostratigraphic units (Appendix).

Thickness maps of individual lithostratigraphic units were also produced (Appendix – II-16, II-23, II-28, II-33, II-39), which were also partly used to check the correctness of the created structure maps.

List of created thickness maps:

- thickness map of the Paleogene
- thickness map of the Mikulov formation
- thickness map of the Vranovice formation
- thickness map of the Nikolcice formation
- thickness map of the Carboniferous

The depth contours of the individual maps (surfaces) in digital format were then gridded within the extent of 3D seismic cube with 10 x 10 m increment, which allowed the created surfaces to be displayed in 3D (Fig. 4-11 – 4-19). Via export and then import, it was possible to use all the programs used for 3D visualization and possible further work. After importing the surfaces into Petrel, a 3D grid was created with a grid increment of 10 m and a vertical depth range of 0 - 3000 m (TVDSS) and within almost the entire extent of the 3D seismic area. All surfaces from previous interpretations and mapping were added to the 3D grid and zones were created between them, representing geological / stratigraphic units. The individual parts of the geological model in Petrel are shown in Appendix – II-1 – II-10. Using the MOVE software, into which the surfaces were also imported, it was then possible to direct export to a 3D pdf file showing the created geological model in a 3D environment without the need for specialised geological or visualisation software.

Fig. 4-11: 3D view of the base of Carboniferous in depth domain (in OpenTect).

Fig. 4-12: 3D view of the base of Jurassic in depth domain (in OpendTect).

Fig. 4-13: 3D view of the top of the Nikolcice formation in depth domain (in OpendTect).

Fig. 4-14: 3D view of the top of the Vranovice formation in depth domain (in OpendTect).

Fig. 4-15: 3D view of the base of Paleogene in depth domain (in OpendTect).

Fig. 4-16: 3D view of the base of Flysch nappes in depth domain (in OpendTect).

Fig. 4-17: 3D view of all surfaces in depth domain in OpendTect.

Fig. 4-18: 3D view of all surfaces in depth domain in Petrel.

Fig. 4-19: 3D view of surfaces in depth domain in MOVE.

4.4 Layering

Several iterations of layering of each zone within the model were made to cover considered possibilities of geological evolution of the Zar-3 structure. First model iteration (50x50 m original grid) was populated by the layers only in reservoir formations

area, using the follow-base type layering and the 10 m cell thickness for each layer within the reservoir zone. After incorporation of overburden, the density of layers was increased to 5 m thickness in the reservoir zone, and 10 m thickness was preserved in the Paleogene and Mikulov Marl zones (Fig. 4-20). Follow-base, follow-top and follow subhorizontal surface geometries were tested in all zones and all segments (Fig. 4-21) to provide the best possible representation of real geological development of the area.

For the final iteration, the follow-top geometries for all zones were chosen and layers were prepared in 1 m interval for reservoir formations (Vranovice Fm. and Nikolčice Fm.), and 10 m interval for the rest of non-reservoir formations (Fig. 4-22). For testing of dynamic modelling parameters, special layering was prepared with sub-horizontal layers within the reservoir formations (Fig. 4-23).

Fig. 4-20: 3D grid with initial grid size, 5 m layer interval in reservoir zones and 10 m layer interval in non-reservoir zones.

Fig. 4-21: 3D grid with follow-top layering (left) vs follow-base layering (right) in the Mikulov Marl zone.

Fig. 4-22: Final grid iteration with 1 m layering interval in the reservoir Vranovice Fm. zone.

Fig. 4-23: 3D grid with sub-horizontal layering in reservoir facies zones.

5 DISTRIBUTION OF PETROPHYSICAL PROPERTIES IN THE STORAGE COMPLEX

After detailed interpretation of 3D seismic, construction of surfaces of key horizons and construction of the static reservoir model in the Petrel software the petrophysical properties were distributed within the final model grid of the core reservoir model. The porosity and permeability were distributed in the reservoir rocks (Vranovice Fm. and Nikolčice Fm.) in both segments, the main, central one covering directly the CO₂ injection structure, as well as in the larger segment covering the adjacent aquifer zone (Fig. 1-3).

The basic input for the reservoir properties distribution were the well log results in discrete wells, which were interpreted for MND a.s. by Hrubý (2004, 2011) to provide the porosity and permeability values in reservoir intervals of the Zar-3 field production wells. The wells in the aquifer part of the reservoir within the model grid were re-interpreted by MND a.s.

The PowerLog software was used for the interpretation of petrophysical properties in the wells in the oil and gas zone of Zar-3 field while the Interactive Petrophysics software was used for the aquifer part within the model grid.

5.1 Well logs evaluation

The production wells logs were interpreted for MND a.s. by Hrubý (2004, 2011) in detail, the wells in the aquifer part of the model grid were also interpreted recently. The Gamma-ray, Spontaneous potential, Resistivity log, Neutron log, Density and Sonic logs were used for interpretation. These were complemented by the Caliper log and NMR (nuclear magnetic resonance) data if available. The data were generally assessed to be of good quality (Hrubý 2004, 2011). Data from well tests and temperature logging were used for the temperature profile of the area; these were available for the ZA3, UH3, ZA4A, ZA5H, ZA6 and ZA6A wells.

Several techniques were used for the porosity calculation (density – neutron cross-plot – see Fig. 5-1, interpretation of density, neutron and sonic logs) depending on availability of the logs in discrete wells. The resulting porosity was corrected for the clay minerals presence and thus the final calculated porosities are effective ones. The water saturation S_w values were calculated from the resistivity of the formation water, effective porosity, cementing factor and Archie's constant. The permeability was calculated from the effective porosity values and water saturation values, using the Timur formula.

Fig. 5-1: Cross-plot chart of PORN (neutron porosity) – HK (density).

5.2 Well logs upscaling

17 wells including sidetracks, present within the Zar-3 site (where the model reservoir facies of Vranovice and Nikolčice Fm. occur) were used for basic reservoir properties upscale process using property modelling module of Petrel. The following wells were used: UH3, UH5, UH6, ZA1, ZA3, ZA4, ZA4A, ZA5H, ZA6, ZA6A, ZA7, ZA8AH, ZA8H, ZA9AH, ZA9H, ZA12 and ZA14H.

The well logs interpretations described in chapter 5.1 were loaded to Petrel software and the upscale process was done separately for the effective porosity (PHIEQ) and permeability (KABS) values, using the same arithmetic average method. The upscale process was done in a significant number of iterations, since for each grid change, each zone change or each change in layering the upscaling process has to be done individually. The final well upscale example for the wells ZA3 and ZA4A is shown in Figs. 5-2 and 5-3.

Fig. 5-2: Well ZA3 - depths, well logs and upscaled values of porosity (PHIEQ) and permeability (KABS).

Fig. 5-3: Well ZA4A - depths, well logs and upscaled values of porosity (PHIEQ) and permeability (KABS).

5.3 3D Petrophysical properties distribution

After the upscale of all available well logs within the model grid, the distribution of porosity and permeability within the final model grid was done. As the static model deals mostly with the carbonate type of reservoir in relatively large area, with only locally denser dataset, the Gaussian sequential simulation was chosen as the property distribution method. This is a stochastic method based on kriging but capable of capturing extreme values in a heterogeneous reservoir. The properties should honour the wells results, histogram and variogram with same variability image over the model.

Fig. 5-4: The 3D view on first grid iteration (25 x 25 m) with 3D porosity distribution.

Fig. 5-5: The final iteration of 3D grid with porosity distributions (10 x 10 m horizontal grid + 1 m thickness of vertical layers) demonstrated in a reservoir cross-section.

Fig. 5-6: The reservoir engineering version of final iteration of 3D grid with porosity distributions (sub horizontal layering - 10 x 10 m horizontal grid + 1 m thickness of vertical layers).

Firstly, the variograms and variogram maps were constructed and the anisotropy was tested for a dataset, which was upscaled from the calculated well logs. Several major direction azimuths were tested in variograms ranging from the 0 – 35 degrees and anisotropy range was tested from 250 m to 2500 m in major direction and 150 m to 2500 m in minor direction using the spherical variogram. Finally, as the only denser part of the dataset is concentrated in segment 2 covering only the direct vicinity of the Zar-3 site and the data in the rest of the aquifer are rather scarce, the isotropic distribution with the anisotropy range 1250 m in both directions was used for both reservoir zones.

The distribution was done in several iterations for different grid iterations. The first iteration of property modelling was done using the 25 x 25 m grid with 5 m layer interval in reservoir zones (Fig. 5-4), while the last iterations were using horizontal grid density of 10x10 m with either 1 m layer thickness following the base of the reservoir zone (Fig. 5-5), or 1 m layer thickness with horizontal layering (Fig. 5-6).

Different distributions were gradually tested by reservoir engineers to match the known volume of hydrocarbons and to match the production results in the discrete parts of the grid penetrated by the production wells. Finally the 10 x 10 m grid with follow base layering was chosen as the working one with the supplementary 10 x 10 m grid with horizontal layering. The resulting cross-sections of porosity and permeability distributions are demonstrated in Figs. 5-7 to 5-10 and the maps of petrophysical properties in the working segment 2 area in Figs. 5-11 to 5-14.

Fig. 5-7: Porosity distribution in 3D – J direction cross-section – position at ZA6A well.

Fig. 5-8: Porosity distribution in 3D – J direction cross-section – position at ZA3 well.

Fig. 5-9: Porosity distribution in 3D – J direction cross-section – position at ZA9AH well.

Fig. 5-10: Porosity distribution in 3D – J direction cross-section – position at ZA5H well.

Fig. 5-11: Permeability distribution map – K direction cross-section – position in 3D in the lower right corner (grid level 1860 m at ZA6A).

Fig. 5-12: Permeability distribution map – K direction cross-section – position in 3D in the lower right corner (grid level - 1815 m depth at ZA6A well).

Fig. 5-13: Porosity distribution map – K direction cross-section – position in 3D in the lower right corner (grid level – 1815 m at ZA6A well).

Fig. 5-14: Porosity distribution map – K direction cross-section – position in 3D in the lower right corner (grid level – 1860 m at ZA6A well).

6 CONCLUSION

Project result V1 - 3D geological model of the storage complex and set of structural geological maps – is the main achievement of Work Package 2 (WP2) of CO₂-SPICER project. The key activity was the construction of a detailed reservoir model of Zar-3 potential CO₂ storage site, corresponding to a currently produced oil and gas field in the production licences "Žarošice" and "Žarošice I", held by the company MND a.s. This model was prepared as the main input for the dynamic modelling of fluids behaviour in the reservoir zone during the remaining hydrocarbon production and CO₂ injection. In addition, a simplified regional geological model of the whole storage complex was constructed, embracing also the overlying geological lithostratigraphic units, to provide information about the caprock (sealing) formations and possible interactions between different rock formations during the CO₂ injection.

3D seismic data together with information obtained from the deep wells drilled during the oil and gas exploration and production in the area represent the main input for model building. The seismic data were carefully interpreted in all stratigraphic levels. Time maps of key horizons were constructed from seismic interpretations and converted to the depth domain, using the velocity model obtained from the measurements in deep exploration wells in the area. After the basic geological (geometric) model was constructed in 3D, a static reservoir model in Schlumberger Petrel© software environment was created, using many iterations to provide the best information about possible geological evolution of the area. A significant amount of iterations was performed during the static model preparation as the complexity of the geological settings of the area allows for several possible solutions. The final static model iteration was finally prepared for property modelling (distribution of reservoir properties), fracture modelling and consequently for direct import into the dynamic modelling software¹.

Novelty and main benefits of the result

The static geological model of the Zar-3 storage complex is completely novel - for the first time a 3D model is available for a broader interpretational area covering not only the Zar-3 field structure, but also its large aquifer zone and surrounding geological formations. The newest exploration results represented by the ZA12 well were also used to specify the spill point of the structure in detail. As the model is covering the potential future CO₂ storage, the zones of the sealing formations (caprock) were also incorporated into the model to cover the complex geological development of the area in three-dimensional space.

Expected use of the result

In the first phase, i.e. within project duration, the result will serve as pivotal input into other project WPs, especially the dynamic modelling and simulations of CO₂ injection in WPs 3 and 8, assessment of risks and possible CO₂ leakage pathways in WP6 and setting-up the Site monitoring plan in WP7. In addition, the model and maps will serve as the main source of data to present and visualise the storage site to the outer world, to all target groups of project communication and dissemination activities. The main end-users of the result in this phase will be the project partners who will utilise it in follow-up project Work Packages as described above.

¹ Project results R2.2-R2.7 provide a more-detailed description of individual phases and components of 3D modelling performed in Work Package 2.

In the post-project phase, the result, and especially the 3D reservoir model as its core part, will represent a key component of geological information on the Zar-3 field that will be necessary for planning and preparation of any subsequent activity related to the field utilisation. In the optimum case, i.e. if the scenarios for using the field as a CO₂ storage site, as prepared within the project, are realised, the model will be a crucial part of the documentation to support the CO₂ storage permit application and all the other documents related to the storage site construction, CO₂ injection and site monitoring. The model will also be used for any other possible use of the Zar-3 field that may be considered, starting from optimisation of the production of remaining hydrocarbons to free the available pore space, through possible use for storage of other gases than CO₂ (hydrogen, natural gas, synthetic gases), up to possible utilisation of geothermal energy contained in the reservoir and reservoir fluids. The key end-user in this phase will be project partner MND. MND will use the result, and especially its key component - the 3D reservoir model - for any future activities related to the Zar-3 field, as indicated above. These activities can be both non-commercial (e.g. research, pilot and demonstration activities) and commercial (e.g. offering CO₂ storage as a service to CO₂ emitters).

Resources used as input for elaboration of the result

A huge dataset comprising data from the Zar-3 site and the surrounding area, collected in WP1, was used for creation of the 3D model and the derived set of maps. The dataset includes all exploration wells final reports, well logs, well test evaluations, stratigraphic studies and, last but not least, the large 3D seismic data cube necessary for geological interpretation of both reservoir and sealing rocks.

Both versions of the 3D geological model – the core reservoir model and the simplified regional model of the storage complex - are presented and visualised in Appendix 1 to this report in form of 3D model views and structural geological maps.

REFERENCES

Hrubý, J., 2004. Závěrečná zpráva. Petrofyzikální analýza ropo-plynového ložiska Žarošice. MS. MND a.s. Archive, Hodonín. (Czech only)

Hrubý, J., 2011. Závěrečná zpráva. Dodatečné vyhodnocení vrtů ZA9AH a Za14H a MDT měření ve vrtu ZA6a, ložisko Žarošice. MS. MND a.s. Archive, Hodonín. (Czech only)

APPENDICES

Appendix 1: 3D model views and structural geological maps

List of figures in Appendix 1:

PART I

Core 3D reservoir model of Zar-3 structure

- I-1: View of the top of Vranovice Fm.
- I-2: Porosity distribution
- I-3: Permeability distribution
- I-4: View of the top of Nikolčice Fm.
- I-5: View of the top of Mikulov marl
- I-6: View of the top of Mikulov marls with added cross-section
- I-7: Depth map - Base of Carpathian thrust units
- I-8: Depth map - Top of Paleogene
- I-9: Depth map - Top of Mikulov marl
- I-10: Depth map - Top of Vranovice Fm.
- I-11: Depth map - Top of Nikolčice Fm
- I-12: Depth map - Top of Lower Carboniferous
- I-13: Depth map - initial water-oil (W-O) and oil-gas (O-G) contact in Vranovice Fm
- I-14: Depth map - current W-O and O-G contact in Vranovice Fm
- I-15: Depth map - initial W-O and O-G contact in Nikolčice Fm
- I-16: Depth map - current W-O and O-G contact in Nikolčice Fm

Part II

Simplified regional 3D geological model of Zar-3 storage complex

- II-1: 3D view of the top of the pre-Carboniferous and pre-Jurassic basement
- II-2: 3D view of the top of the Carboniferous
- II-3: 3D view of the top of the Nikolčice Fm.
- II-4: 3D view of the top of the Vranovice Fm.
- II-5: 3D view of the top of the Mikolov Fm.
- II-6: 3D view of the top of the Paleogene
- II-7: 3D view of the stratigraphic succession
- II-8: 3D view of units below the Vranovice Fm.
- II-9: 3D view of the Vranovice Fm.
- II-10: 3D view of the caprock sealing the Vranovice Fm.
- II-11: Depth structure map of the base of the Flysch belt units
- II-12: Depth structure map of the base of the Flysch belt units - underlying formations

- II-13: Depth structure map of the top of the Paleogene
- II-14: Depth structure map of the base of the Paleogene
- II-15: Depth structure map of the base of the Paleogene - underlying formations
- II-16: Thickness map of the Paleogene
- II-17: Depth structure map of the top of the Jurassic
- II-18: Depth structure map of the top of the Jurassic - overlaying formations
- II-19: Depth structure map of the top of the Mikulov Fm.
- II-20: Depth structure map of the top of the Mikulov Fm. - overlaying formations
- II-21: Depth structure map of the base of the Mikulov Fm.
- II-22: Depth structure map of the base of the Mikulov Fm. - underlying formations
- II-23: Thickness map of the Mikulov Fm.
- II-24: Depth structure map of the top of the Vranovice Fm.
- II-25: Depth structure map of the top of the Vranovice Fm. - overlaying formations
- II-26: Depth structure map of the base of the Vranovice Fm.
- II-27: Depth structure map of the base of the Vranovice Fm. - underlying formations
- II-28: Thickness map of the Vranovice Fm.
- II-29: Depth structure map of the top of the Nikolčice Fm.
- II-30: Depth structure map of the top of the Nikolčice Fm. - overlaying formations
- II-31: Depth structure map of the base of the Nikolčice Fm.
- II-32: Depth structure map of the base of the Nikolčice Fm. - underlying formations
- II-33: Thickness map of the Nikolčice Fm.
- II-34: Depth structure map of the base of the Jurassic
- II-35: Depth structure map of the base of the Jurassic - underlying formations
- II-36: Depth structure map of the top of the Carboniferous
- II-37: Depth structure map of the top of the Carboniferous - overlaying formations
- II-38: Depth structure map of the base of the Carboniferous
- II-39: Thickness map of the Carboniferous

This report is a result of the CO₂-SPICER project
(CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir) - project No: TO01000112.

The CO₂-SPICER project benefits from a €2.32 mil. grant
from Norway and Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.

More information about the project can be found at
co2-spicer.geology.cz.

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

Programme **Kappa**

T A
Č R